

Social Media Usage and Body Image Issues in Indian Adolescents

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ABSTRACT

Social media is now one of the prime platforms used for communication by teens and plays an indispensable role in their lives. There is abundance of evidence to suggest that excessive use of social media leads to many problems, such as cyberbullying and risky behavior among adolescents. There have been a lot of concerns regarding the promotion of unrealistic body image on social media. Body dissatisfaction is experienced when one holds negative thoughts about one's body and thinks they have failed to meet the standards of the society. This study assesses the correlation between body image and social media usage and also examines if females' and males' body image issues are affected equally by the negative impact of social media. The data was gathered from high school students who belonged to the age group of 15-18 years. The study consisted of a convenience sample of 57 Indian participants from Jaipur, Rajasthan. The study used two standardized scales- the Social Media Engagement Scale for Adolescents (Ni et al., 2020) and the Adolescent Body Image Satisfaction Scale (Leone et al., 2014). The correlation analyses revealed that there is no significant correlation between Social Media Engagement Scale and Body Image Satisfaction in both males and females ($r = 0.108$; $p < 0.01$).

Keywords: *Social Media Usage, Indian Adolescents, Body Image Satisfaction*

1. INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a pivotal phase which is marked by many biological, social, and psychological changes in young individuals. A sense of identity and greater autonomy is developed, new skills and responsibilities are acquired and strong relationships are built (O'Reilly et al., 2018). These relationships are built through socialization with peers and parents, in school, and through social media. Social media is now an indispensable platform which is used for communication by almost everyone and plays an important role in their lives. Social media use amongst adolescents has excessively increased in recent years. India

has the second-largest social media user population, which includes 755.47 million users. Among them, more than half of the Indian youth spend over 3 hours daily on social media (Reid & Weigle, 2014). It is widely accepted through many researches that overutilization of social media negatively impacts the Indian youth. Such impacts can be on an individual's mental health as well as physical health, for instance, mental fatigue, strain, anxiety, and feeling panic-stricken (Singh et al., 2017).

Social media addiction is a behavioral addiction that is characterized by having an excessive preoccupation with social media, being driven by an uncontrollable urge to log on to or use social media, and spending so much time and effort on social media that it negatively impacts other important areas of life. Over the last decade, checking and scrolling through social media has flourished which can result in further impairment of important areas of life. (Hou et al., 2019). Primarily, it was seen that in the last two years, social media was used excessively during the pandemic. Social media has become one of the most important and popular means to spread information during the pandemic. Not only this, absorbing disaster-related content on social media is related with negative mental health (Zhao & Zhou, 2020). Thus, social media use during the pandemic contributed to more mental health issues like secondary traumatic stress, depression, low self-esteem and anxiety.

There is increasing evidence to suggest that extreme use of social media leads to many problems, such as cyberbullying and risky behavior among adolescents. With the growing of social media usage, cyberbullying has gained notable attention. Numerous studies have shown that cyberbullying can have serious mental health consequences. Both the victims and offenders of cyberbullying tend to have higher rates of depression, lower self esteem, school and academic problems, more delinquent behaviors, and higher rates of suicide (Reid & Weigle, 2014). Many theories suggest that there is a profound influence and pressure on adolescents to engage in risky behavior such as substance abuse and alcohol consumption, which is supported by reinforcements such as 'likes' and 'comments' (Vannucci et al., 2020).

In addition to this, there have been a lot of concerns regarding the promotion of unrealistic body image on social media (Sagrera et al., 2022). Body image relates to how individuals perceive and feel about their own bodies. A person's feelings, thoughts, and perception about his or her body is also related to body image. In this context, body image concerns are typically understood to include "unrealistic body size estimation, evaluation of body attractiveness, and emotions associated with body shape and size." Also "with the growing sense of the ideal body image, adolescents try to gain or lose weight to attain the perfect body" (Ganesan et al., 2018). Body dissatisfaction is experienced when one holds negative

thoughts about their body (Gorgan, 2021). The ideal image that is expected of adolescents varies across genders. While women are expected to be slim, men are expected to be lean but muscular as well (Mills et al., 2017). In the Indian context, Indian female adolescents have excessive concerns about body weight, body image, and socio-cultural attitudes toward appearance (Rashmi, 2016). Indian males tend to think of the ideal body image as having an unrealistic and unattainable muscular body portrayed by the media, which has a negative impact on the mental health of these individuals (Sampath et al., 2020).

To summarize, adolescents have always been pressured to have the “ideal” body, and this problem is suspected to grow even more grave with the increase of social media. The pressure related to body image is immense in India as well. Body image dissatisfaction is seen more in urban areas than in rural areas in India. Furthermore, body image dissatisfaction is associated with increased socio-cultural pressure (Ganesan et al., 2018).

Thus, this study aims to assess the relationship between body image and social media usage. This study is essential as some researchers have revealed that females are more affected by social media and its standards for body image, while others say that men are equally affected by this. Thus, through this study, we also examine if males’ and females’ body image are affected equally by the negative impact of social media and gain insights within the scope of our population.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Aim of the study

The present study explores the relationship between body image and social media usage in adolescents.

2.2 Research design

This study has an exploratory correlational research design in which the researcher is interested in how two or more variables affect each other without the controlling or manipulating of any of the variables. The independent variable was the body image of adolescents from which data was collected. This was defined by how comfortable the adolescents were with their own body, how they think other people view their body and what they think a perfect body is. The dependent variable was the usage of social media. This was defined by how much time was given to social media by an adolescent and how important social media was to them in terms of their own comfort and encouragement from others.

2.3 Hypothesis

It was hypothesized that there is no relationship between body image and social media usage in adolescents.

2.4 Consent and ethical considerations

It was made sure that while conducting the study all ethical guidelines of research were followed. Confidentiality and privacy of the participants were sustained. Informed consent was taken from all the participants and the participation was ensured to be voluntary. No data was disclosed to a third party. The participants were asked to reveal only their initials. Also the data was de-identified before conducting the study.

2.5 Sample

The data was collected from high school students who belonged to the age group of 15-18 years. The study consisted of a convenience sample of 57 Indian participants from Jaipur, Rajasthan. The data collection was done from 18 males and 39 females. The data was collected from students who could read and write in English.

2.6 Measures

Two standardized scales were used to gather data on the variables addressed in the study.

i) Social Media Engagement Scale For Adolescents

This 13-item scale (Ni et al., 2020) was used to determine how adolescents engage with social media and its effect on their health. This scale has three subscales. The Cronbach's α of the 3 subscales range from 0.709 to 0.804 indicating that the measure is fairly reliable. Cognitive subscale refers to the understanding of certain issues which could reflect a person's perception. The emotional subscale refers to the emotions of an individual's problems which could be positive or negative and the effect they have on getting involved with each other. Finally, the behavioral subscale is referred to the habitual activities that an individual engages in. The response pattern is on a "5-point Likert scale (Strongly Disagree = 5, Disagree = 4, undecided = 3, Agree = 2, Strongly Agree = 1)." It includes items like "using social media is my daily habit", "I get fulfilled from the attention and comments of others on social media", "I feel anxious when I can't use social media". This scale was used because it was made specifically for adolescents and had high reliability and validity.

ii) Adolescent Body Image Satisfaction Scale (ABISS)

This is a 16-item, age-appropriate measure (Leone et al., 2014) that determines body image satisfaction. The test was reliable as indicative of Bartlett's test of sphericity which was statistically significant ($\chi^2 (120) = 1666.31, p \leq 0.05$). ABISS consists of three subscales. Weighted omega for all the 3 subscales was above or equal to 0.64 which makes the scale reliable as well. The first one is body competence, which explains how people may positively value the development of their body. The second subscale is body image, encompassing interpersonal and social influences and how their internalization shapes one's perception of their body image. Internal conflict is the third subscale that balances an adolescent's positive and negative perceptions of body image. The response pattern is on a "4-point Likert scale (Strongly Disagree = 4, Disagree = 3, Agree = 2, Strongly Agree = 1)." It includes items like "I am satisfied with my body", "I will people ignore me because of my looks", "there is no perfect body". Leone et al., 2014, in their study, revealed that this scale has high content validity and initial construct validity. This scale was originally made for male adolescents, but the items were gender-neutral, so the study scale is used for both male and female adolescents.

2.7 Demographics

The demographic information which was collected from participants included age, gender, and ethnicity. The living situation, number of siblings, and family type of the participants was also reported.

2.8 Data collection and analysis procedure

Data was collected through an anonymous and voluntary Google form survey, which was circulated online. Respondents not falling within the age group being addressed in the study were excluded. Data from adolescents with serious mental health issues or psychiatric illness in the present or past was also excluded. The data was analyzed using SPSS version 29. This study conducted two analytical methods: An independent sample *t*-test and Pearson's correlation test. The differences between males' and females' body image as a result of social media usage was analyzed by an independent *t*-test. To understand the association between the variables a correlation test was conducted.

3. RESULTS

Table 1 shows the correlation among all the variables in the study

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Behavioural ¹ engagement subscale	1	.902**	.056	.894**	-.039	.142	.072	.066
Cognitive ² engagement subscale	.902**	1	.117	.932**	-.062	.123	.135	.063
Affective ³ engagement subscale	.056	.117	1	.431**	.093	.182	.041	.138
Total of ⁴ social media engagement scale	.894**	.932**	.431**	1	-.017	.184	.115	.108
Body incompetenc e subscale	-.039	-.062	.093	-.017	1	.601**	.380**	.845**
Body ⁶ Inadequacy subscale	.142	.123	.182	.184	.601	1	.593**	.899**
Internal ⁷ conflict subscale	.072	.135	.041	.115	.380**	.593**	1	.718**
Total of ⁸ ABISS	.066	0.63	.138	.108	.845**	.899**	.718**	1

Table 2 shows the results for the t-test between social media engagement and adolescent body image satisfaction

	F	p	t
Total of social media engagement scale	.308	.581	.075
Total of ABISS	.008	.931	-.459

The data was normally distributed based on the Shapiro-Wilk normality testing in which the total social media engagement subscale was ($p = 0.797, 0.203$) for females and males respectively, and for the total ABISS was ($p = 0.856, 0.374$) for females and males respectively. Based on the data acquired from the 57 participants, the results of the correlational analysis suggest that there is no significant relationship between social media and body image dissatisfaction ($r = 0.108, p < 0.01$). The results can be due to the fact that this study has a limited sample size; thus, no significant relationship was discerned between the subscales of the two scales. Due to the small number of participants the results may be less generalized to identify significant associations.

An independent t-test was conducted to compare 18 males' and 37 females' social media engagement and adverse body image. t-test results showed no significant difference in mean social media engagement scores between male and female groups, with equal variances assumed ($t(53) = 0.075, p = 0.581$). Similarly, t-test results indicated no significant difference in variances of body image between male and female groups, with equal variances assumed ($t(53) = -0.459, p = 0.931$). This signifies that there was no difference between males and females in terms of body image issues and social media usage.

		Shapiro-Wilk		
subscale	gender	statistic	df	sig.
Behavioral engagement subscale	female	.938	37	.039
	male	.875	18	.022
Cognitive engagement subscale	female	.966	37	.309
	male	.945	18	.351
Affective engagement subscale	female	.965	37	.280
	male	.835	18	.005
Total of social media subscale	female	.982	37	.797
	male	.931	18	.203
Body incompetence subscale	female	.978	37	.657
	male	.963	18	.658
Body inadequacy subscale	female	.972	37	.467
	male	.978	18	.925
Internal conflict subscale	female	.962	37	.232
	male	.956	18	.522
Total of ABISS	female	.984	37	.856
	male	.947	18	.374

4. DISCUSSION

Our study found that there is no significant relationship between social media use and body image dissatisfaction among Indian adolescents. Some studies revealed similar findings. Cohen et al. (2017) found that while photo-based activities on Facebook and Instagram are linked to body image dissatisfaction, the overall social media use may not be. Another study found that exposure to social media does not directly influence a woman's body satisfaction. Moreover, social media affects women who tend to make social comparisons more (Fardouly et al., 2015).

However, most research done on this matter proposes that increased engagement in social media by both men and women is associated with a higher likelihood of body image dissatisfaction_(Salomon & Brown, 2018). This signifies that it is important to note the cultural differences when looking at these results. Also, in terms of the gender based distinction, a study conducted by Sagrera et al. (2022) found that females are more affected by the relationship between social media usage and body image dissatisfaction. The study by Sagrera et al., (2022) and many others done on this matter were conducted before COVID-19, and it is essential to understand how the dynamics have evolved since then. The social media usage has seen a significant increment during and after the pandemic, it is important to take these circumstances into consideration as well (Zhao & Zhou, 2020).

Studies on Indian adolescents relating to social media engagement and body image dissatisfaction have been very inconsistent and underexplored, which could explain why the results of this study are so different from many other research papers. A new population was taken into account, on which research has not been done before.

The results of this study contribute greatly to understanding mental health issues among Indian adolescents. This study is valuable for healthcare professionals in understanding and supporting adolescents' mental well-being and spreading awareness about the effects of excessive social media usage.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, by examining data collected from adolescents from Jaipur, Rajasthan, this study found that there is no significant relationship between body image and social media engagement. This study also found that there is no difference between males' and females' body image and social media usage. However, in light of this matter, more studies are needed to evaluate the impact of social media on an Indian adolescent's mental health.

6. LIMITATIONS

These findings must be viewed after considering the following limitations: a relatively small sample size was taken due to the timeframe. The small number of participants may decrease the generalizability of the results and may not be representative of a larger population. The participants were from Jaipur, Rajasthan, which may also decrease the generalizability of the results and limit the generalizability to the population of Rajasthan. The characteristics and behaviors of participants in this particular location may not represent those from other parts of India as it is a very diverse country.

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